

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PROFESSIONAL MOTIVES
IN STUDENTS

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Annotation. Vocational guidance of students is the basis for determining the student's personality as a future professional. In vocational guidance, it is necessary to provide and form knowledge about the world of professions to a large number of people, taking into account their abilities, needs, desires, wishes, opportunities, individual characteristics, etc. The development of vocational motives among students during the educational process ensures the success of future professional activities and reduces the consequences of the crisis of professional development. In this article, we have highlighted the importance of vocational guidance of students and vocational motives.

Keywords: choice of profession, vocational guidance, teacher, student, vocational motivation, interest, ability

Аннотация. Профориентация является основой формирования будущей карьеры студента. При ориентации людей на карьеру важно обучать и формировать их представления о мире профессий, принимая во внимание их способности, потребности, желания, стремления, возможности, индивидуальные особенности и т. д. Развитие профессиональной мотивации у студентов в процессе обучения обеспечивает успешность будущей профессиональной деятельности и снижает последствия кризиса профессионального развития. В этой статье мы подчеркнули важность профессиональной ориентации и карьерной мотивации для студентов.

Ключевые слова: выбор карьеры, профориентация, учитель, ученик, карьерная мотивация, интерес, способность

Anotatsiya. O'quvchilarni kasbga yo'naltirish bu o'quvchi shaxsini kelajakdagi kasb egasi bo'lishini belgilab berish asosi hisoblanadi. Kasbga yo'naltirishda ko'prok insonlarni o'z qobiliyatlari, extiyojlari, xoxish, istaklari, imkoniyatlari, individual xususiyatlari va xokazolarni hisobga olgan holda kasblar olami haqida bilim berish va shakllantirish lozim. O'quv jarayonida o'quvchilar o'rtasida kasbiy motivlarning rivojlanishi kelajakda kasbiy faoliyatning muvaffaqiyatini ta'minlaydi va kasbiy rivojlanish inqirozining oqibatlarini kamaytiradi. Ushbu maqolada o'quvchilarni kasbga yo'naltirish va kasb motivlarining ahamiyatini yoritib berdik.

Kalit so'zlar: kasb tanlash, kasbga yo'naltirish, o'qituvchi, o'quvchi, kasb motivatsiyasi, qiziqish, qobiliyat

Introduction. Choosing a profession is one of the most important events that determine a person's life path, therefore, the need for scientific research of this process arises. For example, professional self-determination of students is often carried out unconsciously, under the influence of parents and friends, which leads to personnel turnover in enterprises, and to the violation of the professional choice of young people.

The negative consequences of an incorrectly chosen profession due to personal psychological characteristics affect both the person himself and his work environment. They are manifested in depressive states, a negative perception of the world, aggression, and depression. This determines the need to inform secondary school students about the issues of professional self-determination and the formation of conscious motives in choosing a profession. Most students, having mastered the basics of science during their studies, form a certain idea, and think about the professions they like. It is necessary to take into account the inclinations, passions, aspirations, desires, motives, and good intentions of schoolchildren, especially the emergence of interests, motives, and aspirations for a particular profession. Taking into account the individual typological characteristics, age and gender of students, directing each of them to a reasonable profession is one of the important tasks of a psychologist, teacher and parents.

Discussion. It should not be forgotten that teaching students to independently choose a profession, to self-assess their capabilities, is a very important and necessary task. Therefore, psychologists, methodologists, and diagnostic center employees, together with the general public, should widely promote vocational knowledge, develop guidelines and methods for choosing a profession, expand the official branches

of career counseling, and increase the scope of professional profiles, professional graphics, and psychograms.

Observations conducted in recent years have shown that there are many shortcomings in the field of vocational guidance of young people in our Republic. We can see this both in the regions and in the recommendations for graduates of grades 9-11 in the Republic [1]. Indeed, the first steps in the implementation of psychological and pedagogical diagnostics and vocational guidance of students have begun at school. We believe that this first step should consist of organizing the staff of a specialist in vocational guidance in schools, as well as a school psychologist who will be engaged in determining the interests, inclinations and abilities of students in the profession. Because without these specialists, it is impossible to even talk about these works in schools.

Motives for choosing a profession are expressed in the general direction of a person, they are always considered inextricably linked and complement each other. This, in turn, is based on the meaning and goals of life, position in society, values, ideals, motives, life plans and worldviews of a person.

Literature analysis. Career guidance today is not just about a person's adaptation to professional work, but also about the acquisition of specific professional knowledge, skills and qualifications, as well as their entry into the world of professions in general. G.V. Kudryavtsev, E.A. Klimov, B.F. Lomov, K.K. Platonov, I.M. Kondakov, K.M. Gurevich and others contributed to the study of career guidance and professional motivation [2].

Russian psychologist E.A. Klimov in his research works paid attention to this very issue, that is, to such issues as “choice of profession”, “orientation to profession”, and conducted research on this issue. In particular, he used the “Differential Diagnostic Questionnaire” (DDS) methodology as an example. In addition to E.A. Klimov, many foreign scientists have also worked on this issue. Gradually, conscious approaches to choosing a profession began to be observed in society [3].

In the USA, great achievements have been made in terms of interest in the profession, the study of qualifications and abilities, and their application in practice. These are mainly reflected in the taxonomy of human activities and abilities created in the scientific work of E. Fleishman, the well-established system of career guidance and selection, and the availability of their services via the Internet [4].

The famous Russian psychologist K.K. Platonov believed that “the professional readiness of a specialist is a subjective state of a person’s belief that he is capable and prepared to perform a certain professional activity and his desire to perform it” [5]. The professional readiness of a specialist has a complex, multi-level and visible systemic psychological form, in which, first of all, the personal appearance of a person plays a

key role. At the same time, professional training requires a specialist to have the necessary level of physical health, the formation and development of physical qualities necessary for professional activity. Because any professional activity involves a person's expenditure of some kind of physical energy. The initial and at the same time very important stage of the process of professional formation is the period of choosing a future profession, that is, coming to a specific professional decision. The level of readiness of young people for professional choice does not depend only on the characteristics of the youth, it does not form by itself at a certain age. In the process of professional choice of young people, it is necessary to prepare and educate them through the general influence of society, using pedagogical and psychological methods. An objective assessment of the effectiveness and results of the vocational education process and the correct planning of professional formation require the use of many professional diagnostic methods. It is known that through professional diagnostic methods, a person's talents, abilities, interests, talents, and abilities are diagnosed in relation to the profession. It is important to determine the composition of professional motives on the basis of career choice and orientation.

Result and analysis. In the process of transferring professional knowledge, professional motives should be developed and instilled in them, and students should be shown the most attractive aspects of professional activities. If professional motivation is a set of factors that determine the purposeful activity of behavior in the chosen professional field and the individual's constant interest in their professional activity, then it shapes the strategy of subsequent professional development, determines the success of the labor subject in his further professional activity, and affects the future positive fulfillment of professional work standards.

The reason for the difficulty of choosing an adequate profession is the low level of psychological knowledge among students, which is due to insufficient information about their abilities, individual psychological characteristics, and inclinations. Starting from grades 7-8, when choosing a profession and preparing for it becomes relevant, students begin to think seriously about their future profession, try to assess their psychological and psychophysiological "reserves" [5].

The school begins to assess the subjects of the curriculum from the point of view of their necessity for the future profession. In this case, the main task of adults is to help the student in self-knowledge, in understanding his own capabilities, behavioral motives, individual psychophysiological capabilities, and to actively use this knowledge in the process of professional self-realization.

One of the conditions for the effectiveness of professional activity is the professional training of a specialist. Professional readiness is understood as the degree

to which a person's mental and physical health and qualities correspond to the requirements of the activity he is engaged in.

All work on the development of professional interests of students should serve the correct choice of a profession by students. There are criteria that indicate the readiness of students to choose a profession; cognitive, that is, the presence of information, interest in the profession, practical criteria. To further develop the motives of professional interest in students, we pay attention to the following [6].

1. Taking into account the individual characteristics of the student when guiding him to a profession.
2. Achieving a complete understanding of the profession chosen during his studies.
3. Introducing students to audio and video materials on various professions during the lessons
4. Organizing a career center in the educational institution.
5. Organize meetings with people who have rendered worthy service to the nation through their profession.

This will help students revise their professional decisions and gain motivation for themselves.

Conclusion. The motives for a student's interest in a profession may come from their parents, from interest in or imitation of people they like around them, from movies they have seen or events they have heard. These psychological factors provide the initial impetus for the formation of professional interest in students. The help of educators and psychologists is necessary to determine whether this interest is the right choice for the child in the future.

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